

Doubly-Periodic Synthesis

Otto Ziep

Independent Research, 13089 Berlin, Germany
Email: ottoziep@gmail.com

Abstract

Vacuum energy is understood by one-periodic frequencies with a possible lowering by confined Casimir forces. Doubly-periodic processed vacuum energy is a non-stationary energy state of a complex Lagrangian. It is suspected that a doubly-periodic processing in the vicinity of zeros of zeta functions lowers vacuum energy as compared to a real physical field. This quadratic model compensates positive energy of molecules mainly by dark, complex phantom energy and negligible ion energy. A proposed doubly-periodic synthesis gains cooling energy by a minimum amount of energy. Created matter is a zero-energy state of biomass and dark energy which is capable to compost into a zero-energy state.

Keywords

information density universe, doubly-periodic processing, elliptic involution, breathing modes, atmospheric power plant, bifurcation, one-dimensional chaotic map.

1. Introduction

The present paper describes in high generality breathing modi in information-based universes with two flows each with an infinite number of frequencies. This state of a self-consistent confinement is understandable as a Casimir effect but with complex non-dissipative energies. Rational coordinates x_μ and entropy current densities j_e are like addresses in a computer memory. The quadratic map deserves attention as a minimal regular map and a maximal regular map. Consecutive $\gamma \circ z$ create binary invariants $f(\omega_k)$ and lattice periods $\delta\omega_k$ with complex multiplication (CM). Addition on iterated elliptic curves is in one-to-one relation to bifurcation [1]. Iterated holomorph binary

$$f(\omega) = \begin{pmatrix} f_1 \\ f_2 \end{pmatrix} = \frac{dx + idy}{dz - dt} \simeq D = [\gamma_\mu \gamma_\nu] D_{\mu\nu}$$

in C^∞ ensures Minkowski spacetime by a stereographic holomorphic-meromorphic projection to Riemann sphere with Dirac matrices γ_{mu} . Chaotic sums of iterated $f(\omega)$ with $D^3 \simeq zD^2$ yield Minkowski spacetime exponents e^D which explains the velocity of light c by simplest cycles. This one-dimensional complex self-similar set is an open system fractal zeta universe (FZU). Regular frayed Cayley-Newton iterates are supposed to exist only in the vicinity of nontrivial zeros z_{nt} in a linear expansion of zeta functions. A large number hypothesis (LNH) correlates low and high energies [2, 3]. As shown in Section 2 invariant $f(\omega)$ is conformal stress-energy which offers a technological application described in Section 3. The 10^∞ zoom gauge coupling predicts continuous creation of matter in FZU and lower vacuum densities. The present paper proposes a laboratory to test generation of newly generated matter in FZU which is called doubly-periodic atmospheric power plant (DPAPP). Up to now power plants process subsequent one-periodic cycles. Isothermal and isentropic Carnot processes are e.g. consecutive one-periodic cycles converting vacuum energy ρ_{vac} of one-periodic inertial systems in Minkowski spacetime. In quantum statistics ρ_{vac} are one-periodic zero-point oscillations $\rho_{vac}(QS)$ of periods $1^{1/m}$ where

$$\rho_{vac}(QS) \simeq 10^{50-20} \rho_{vac}(GR).$$

$\rho_{vac}(GR)$ in general relativity is confirmed by experiment. This cosmological constant problem (CCP) is resolvable by unified fields with elliptic involution in an open FZU whereas laws of thermodynamics apply to closed systems [4]. The present paper describes a technology to obtain lower local values $\rho_{vac} < \rho_{vac}(GR)$ by breathing acting doubly-periodic on a bifurcating potential flow. FZU allows local breathing modes as quasi-stationary vacua to extract heat energy in Section 3. Local creation of matter is analogous to a breathing process of living beings. This local Big Bang-Big Rip scenario would preferentially create molecules H_2O and CO_2 [4]. Energies comparable to the Planck energy M_p are detectable by e.g. lightning energy of $1 \text{ GJ} \simeq 10^{-5} \text{ g} \simeq 0.5 \text{ M}_p \simeq 10^{28} \text{ eV}$. The present theory of lightning is that opposite charges (positive and negative) accumulate in different regions. At lightning potential breakdown discharge occurs if an accumulating one-periodic electrical potential up to $10^5 - 10^8 \text{ V}$ in a thundercloud exceeds the insulating capacity of the air, causing a rapid, massive discharge of electricity known as a lightning flash. This theory is extended to terrestrial gamma ray flashes and cosmic rays (CR) [5]. Recently reported evidence indicates apparent ignition of lightning by cosmic-ray showers or from an avalanche of electrons seeded by extraterrestrial cosmic rays [5]. Analogous to CR-lightning coupling FZU is capable to store dark existing energy as complex dark matter of five unified fields instead of electromagnetic polarization induced by clouds. A FZU cosmic-ray-charged-cloud superfluid (CRCCS) stores unified energy in a non-turbulent open system. Tropical regions with highest lightning rates limit DPAPP processing temperatures to about $50 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ in order to avoid lightning which would discharge the CRCCS-atmospheric capacitor. Every stationary point is surrounded by a three-component doubly-periodic stable state in Section 4. Theory and experiment of the open FZU system is sketched in Section 2 and 3. Topological entropy variation by altitude is superimposed by lateral temperature gradients. Already moderate temperature gradients are suspected to induce a bifurcating spacetime (BST) giving complex non-detectable

energies [6] [7]. Non-detectable particles are viewed as complex dark vacuum energy. A Planck energy can be stored permanently as a doubly-periodic cycle by avoiding turbulences. DPAPP tests the ability to generate lower vacuum energy density by doubly-periodic processes by 'creatio ex nihilo' to a certain amount in CR, atmospheric clouds and photosynthesis in [4]. Cloud motion, plant growth (photosynthesis) and CR are united by regular chaotic iterates of complex BST- curvature $f(\omega)$ near simple zeros z_{nt} [4]. Section 6 confirms a cloud radiative forcing triggered by negative phantom dark energy.

2. Atmosphere- an algorithmic chaotic RC circuit

FZU- vacuum energy is fractal. Low iterated k-components is identified as ultra-high energies above the detection limit which is known as the GZK cutoff. The step $k=0$ is above the detection limit. Earth's atmosphere is viewed as being describable by an entire transcendent, smooth one-dimensional complex function related holomorphic-meromorphic to Riemann sphere in variable $z=h+il$ of altitude h and latitude l in tangential plane. The Weierstrass sigma function $\sigma(z) = -\frac{\partial j_\sigma(z)}{\partial z}$ or ξ - function $\xi(z) = -\frac{\partial j_\xi(z)}{\partial z}$ of the Riemann zeta function $\zeta(z)$ represents a quantum Hall topology (QHT) [8] [9]. QHT dynamical variables are non-analytic potential flow lines

$$\phi_\sigma(x, y), \phi_\xi(x, y) : \phi_\sigma(x, y) = j_\sigma(z) + \bar{j}_\sigma(\bar{z})$$

whereas $\partial_z \sigma(z)$ depend on $\partial_z^2 \sigma(z)$ and $\partial_{g_{2,3}} \sigma(z)$ QHT yields the Laplace equation $\partial_z \partial_{\bar{z}} \sigma(z) = 0$. CRCCS is non-turbulent on osculation planes of a twisted cubic C_{tw} in space. The hyperelliptic Kummer surface $K(X(f))$ is parametrized by a quadratic Hermite-Tschirnhausen process $z \leftarrow F(t, z) \simeq \gamma \circ z$. Elliptic and hyperelliptic 'current densities' j_σ or j_ξ are thought as a flow in an atmospheric spherical capacitor circuit

$$j_\sigma = d \int dz \sigma(z) = d \left(\frac{Q}{C} \right) = \frac{1}{4\pi\epsilon\epsilon_0} \left(\frac{1}{R_{++}} - \frac{1}{R_{+-}} + \frac{1}{R_{-+}} - \frac{1}{R_{--}} \right) \quad (1)$$

with two capacitor stripes $z_{nt} = \pm \frac{1}{2} \pm im_n$ for nontrivial zeros $\xi(z_{nt}) = 0$ or $\sigma(z_{nt})$. A quadrupole tensor $d \left(\frac{Q}{C} \right)$ for complex conjugates $\xi(z), \bar{\xi}(z), \xi(\bar{z}), \bar{\xi}(\bar{z})$ depends on four radii $R_{\pm\pm}$ creating a moment of inertia. Variable z , the Legendre module λ and the Weber invariant $f(\omega)$ are interrelated. $K(X(f))$ points are hyperelliptic \wp -functions parametrized by $f = f(\omega)$

$$X(f) = (1, -f, f^2, 1) = (\wp_{\pm\pm}, 1) \simeq \{j_\sigma(u_\pm, u_\pm), 1\} \simeq (T_{++}, T_{+-}, T_{--}, 1) \quad (2)$$

Like $\xi(z)$ the sigma function is entire and allows a Cayley quotient.

$$\sigma(u_\pm) = -\frac{\partial j_\sigma(u_\pm)}{\partial u_\pm} \rightarrow -\frac{\Delta j_\sigma(u_\pm)}{\Delta u_\pm}$$

The discrete \wp -function in (2) transmits to a Schwarzian derivative $\{j_\sigma(u_\pm), u_\pm\}$ as conformal stress-energy $T_{\pm\pm}$ where

$$\{F(t, z), z\} = 6\partial_z \partial_{z'} \ln \frac{\Delta F}{\Delta z} \quad (3)$$

Points on C_{tw} of $K(X)$ are f-parametrized zeros of

$$\sigma(u_{\pm})\sigma(v_{\pm}) \simeq \zeta(z)\zeta(z') \simeq X(f) \otimes X(f) = 0 \quad (4)$$

which is quadratic in stress-energy $T(u_{\pm})[T(z)]$ which allows quadratic f-iterates for $\sigma(u_{\pm})$ in (4). Like a holomorphic-meromorphic transition $dx_{\mu}(f)$ steps $k+1$ and k are involute, i.e. $f(\omega_{k+1})f(\omega_k) \simeq const.$ If $f(\omega_k)$ is diffusive, $f(\omega_{k+1})$ is drifting which requires to map $\zeta(z)$ zeros to its poles. $res\zeta(z)$, the residuum of $\zeta(z)$ is proportional to the regulator $R(\mathbb{K}) = log E_{\nu}$. Its exponential map allows to introduce a complex Lagrangian $L[\nu]$ for units E_{ν} with frequency ν of a number field \mathbb{K}

$$R(\mathbb{K}) \simeq e^{\int d\nu[f(\omega)]logf(\omega)} \simeq e^{\int d\nu[f(\omega)]L(\nu[f(\omega)])} \quad (5)$$

The ideal residuum $res\zeta(z) = 1$ corresponds to an infinite set ν . Residua of the Dedekind zeta function $\zeta(z, \mathbb{K})$ are used to map $\sigma(u)$ zeros for optimal regulator values. $\xi(z)$ -zeros z_{nt} differ from $\sigma(u)$ by replacing the mass m_n in z_{nt} by $\omega \simeq \sqrt{\Delta}$ with discriminant Δ and performing a multiplication over lattice stripes. Eqs. (2) and (4) prove that $f(\omega_k)$ unifies curvature, time and temperature. Iterates $f(\omega_{k+1}) \leftarrow \gamma \circ f(\omega_k)$ is chaotic if $\{F(t, z), z\} < 0$. $\gamma \circ f(\omega)$ is related to rational coordinates by holomorphic functions from Riemann sphere and meromorphic functions from complex plane. Iterates $k \rightarrow k+1$ is entangled and dynamical in FZU [10]. Accordingly, Minkowski spacetime is a mean field where time is quadrupolar, the scale factor (9) and derivatives ∂_z is drift-diffusive. This dualism maps diffusion coefficient D to the velocity of light c

$$D = 1 = \frac{(\Delta u)^2}{\omega} \rightarrow \frac{(\Delta u)^2}{\omega^2 + c} \rightarrow \frac{(\Delta u)^2}{(\Delta \omega)^2} \rightarrow c^2 \quad (6)$$

Stable orbiting laps and Lorentz-invariant are compatible for $f(\omega) = \begin{pmatrix} f_1 \\ f_2 \end{pmatrix}$

$$\gamma \rightarrow \gamma e^{F_{\mu\nu}[\gamma_{\mu}, \gamma_{\nu}]} \rightarrow \gamma e^{i\sigma z} \quad (7)$$

where $dete^{F_{\mu\nu}[\gamma_{\mu}, \gamma_{\nu}]} = 1$ with Dirac matrices γ_{μ} , skew $F_{\mu\nu}$ is equivalent to complex $\omega_{k+1} \rightarrow \omega_k^2 + c$. Simplest γ -cycles written for the drift-diffusion term $\Delta f = (\gamma - 1) \circ f$ as $\gamma \circ \gamma = \gamma$ prove that squared invariants are coordinates. A quadratic map contains alternately coordinates. For fluctuating lattice periods ω coordinates in space are attached to osculating planes and stationary points. Weierstrass zeta function $\zeta(u, \omega_k)$ in $\Delta f_i = \sum_{j=1, \dots, 4} c_{ij} \Delta \zeta(u_j - u_0, \omega_k)$, $i=1, 2, 3$ require four points $j = 1, \dots, 4$ [11]. Complex time $\delta t \rightarrow \delta t^2$ in (5) is related to additive creation of matter $t \rightarrow t^2$ in LNH [3]. Addition on elliptic curves sets lengths δz equivalent to areas δz^2 modulo a cubic invariant $\phi_3(\delta z)$. A cubic congruence $\delta z \bmod \phi_3(\delta z) \simeq \delta z^2 \simeq \delta z^{-1}$ qualifies a quadratic map as involution. Bifurcating chaotic line segments $dl_{xy} \in z = h + il$ store thermal energy $\simeq \vartheta^2(u_k = a_k \omega_k, \omega_k)$ and drift in a global temperature potential

$$V_{T_{global}}(z) = \int \nabla V_{T_{cloud}} dl_{xy} \quad (8)$$

where dl_{xy} are geometric zeta function sequences. In quantum statistics kinematic temperature T_{kin} is real mean energy E_{kin} , i.e. T_{kin} is one-periodic. Complex E_{kin} is collisional damping and. In CRCCS complex

energy is of the order of rest mass, i.e. both energy (time) and temperature are independent doubly-periodic complex quantities of a superfluid flow. Approximating dl_{xy} in (8) by straight lines between z_{nt} is multiplying by a charge e . It is claimed that $V_{T_{global}}(z)$ governs time-thermal cycles in atmosphere, biosphere and geosphere which can be written as a drift-diffusion potential $V_{T_{global}}(z) = T + \mu n[\#z_{nt}]$. The number of zeros $n[\#z_{nt}]$ with Lagrange parameter μ applies to created charge pairs, i.e. CR, organic aerosols, photosynthesis and vegetational air ions [4].

3. Breathing DPAPP

A Carnot process is a thin rectangle of length $t \rightarrow a^k t$ traversed by the number of cycles k . In distinction doubly-periodic complex temperature and entropy is ultra-high complex energy for iterated $t \leftarrow \gamma \circ t$ with $deg(t) = 2^{2^k}$. An open system CRCCS DPAPP contains already an amount of matter with highest information densities, e.g. plant branching and atmospheric-gaseous-liquid-solid slush around the triple point of water (TPW). Instead of one-periodic electromagnetic nonequilibrium artificial photosynthesis a doubly-periodic process is proposed with complex oscillations of temperature and entropy. Already processing by temperature gradients of $10^1 \dots 10^2 \text{ }^\circ K$ on fluctuating time-thermal contours should create complex a finite ρ_{dark} . A test of this model is that the density of ionized particles changes. DPAPP is based on a complex contour for a superfluid flow potential (8) without turbulences. Seasons are simulated changing topological entropy δh_t by altitude δh . Simultaneous temperature gradients $T(z)$ induced e.g. changing radiation frequency and intensity in varying directions on complex plane are suspected to induce BST and CR. A fluctuating contour $\delta T \delta S < 0$ replaces a Carnot process rectangle. Instead of plates and contacts of the atmospheric capacitor DPAPP a Carnot battery thermal energy storage (TES) and thermal to power (T2P) are proposed to control a cooling by phantom energy ρ_{dark} as sketched in Figure 3.

Figure 1: Breathing mode of DPAPP with drift-diffusing doubly-periodic Carnot process. Lower kinetic energy E^{kin} is in inversion to higher tem-

perature T at ground level.

On a closed path between atmosphere and ground level a potential difference $V_a - V_g$ is generated if a certain amount of matter is created which is triggered by existing matter. The encircled area by branches the vertical z -plane into a tree of chaotic flow lines. Within FZU five interaction participate. DPAPP operates as a statistical zoom by $10^{20} \simeq 2^{2^6}$ comparable to the Avogadro constant. Quadratic forces in ρ_m in (4),(11),(3) overwhelm a rest mass threshold which favors statistically organic molecules. Season-dependent DPAPP Big Bang -Big Rip processes create molecules (discriminants [4]) consisting of atoms H, C, O, N [4]. This real matter ρ_m is compensated by complex dark matter ρ_{dark} . Created matter is accompanied by complex phantom energy which induces cooling in DPAPP by a product of low count rate j_{dark} and high energy E_{dark} . DPAPP trigger are existing bifurcating flow lines which are realized at lant growth and near TPW which require low temperature gradients of $10^2 \text{ }^\circ K$. Accordingly, $\pm 50 \text{ }^\circ K$ around $0 \text{ }^\circ C$ could induce ultrahigh CR energies and ρ_{ion} even at ground level [6].

4. Entangled three-component matter

The algorithm is easy to understand by non-stationary distorted contour instead of a constant temperature rectangle with modular unit $\vartheta^2(u = a\omega, \omega)$ for ω_k with rational $a = (a_1, a_2)$ in universal covering u . CR is understandable by theta constant sources [4]. Complex energies are identified with ρ_{dark} where fractional γ create singularities at each second step. The experimental atmospheric temperature gradient is S-shaped: The rate at which temperature changes with altitude has negative differential branches which confirms cubic $f(\omega)$. According to (4) variable $f(\omega)$ iterates the hyperelliptic function $\wp_{\pm\pm}$ i.e. stress-energy. The underdetermined complex Lagrangian $L(\nu[f(\omega)])$ has an infinity of least squares solutions as a branching tree of doubly-periodic $\nu[f(\omega)]$. In natural science the doubly-periodic minimum is seasonal plant growth and birth of livings being. A real minimum $L(\nu[f(\omega)]) = 0$ yields regulator index $R(\mathbb{K}) = 1$. This corresponds to imaginary quadratic fields of norm $f \bar{f} = 1$ which are used in physical field theory. A pure cubic case $R(\mathbb{K}) \geq 1$ is not preferred. Cyclotomic extensions of yield local minima $R(\mathbb{K})$ yield infinitely many local minima $R(\mathbb{K}) \ll 1$ above the theoretical lowest achievable value $\rho_{vac} = 0$ [12]. For quasi-stationary cyclotomic states of a complex Lagrangian with lower vacuum energy density Minkowski spacetime is the real hull due to $D = 1$ for all iterations. The claim that local $L(\nu[f(\omega)])$ minima are charge quanta in nontrivial zeros z_{nt} of holomorphic functions $\xi(z_{nt}) = 0$ or $\sigma(u_{\pm}) = 0$ as solutions of (4) can be tested by measuring a small amount of $\delta\rho_{ion}$. $\sigma(u_{\pm}) = 0$ or $\Delta_h\sigma(z) = 0$ allows $\gamma \circ z$ or $\gamma \circ u$ and $\gamma \circ \xi$ or $\gamma \circ \sigma(u)$ with hyperbolic Laplacian Δ_h . An algebraic map γ branches into the infinity of stable orbiting laps (ion pairs) and unstable bifurcating k -components (CR) [12]. Odd k -components and even k - components yield diffusive $f(\omega_k)$ and drifting $\lambda(\omega_k)$ charges, alternately. Stable laps as oscillations of the Lyapunov- exponent λ_L around zero yield the Lagrangian $L(\nu[f(\omega)]) \simeq \{F, z\} = L(F, \dot{F}, \ddot{F}, \ddot{\ddot{F}})$ in (3),(4) and (5). The discrete γ -invariant derivative already contains the drift-

diffusion scale factor $R \simeq z_{k+1} - z_k$

$$\dot{F} = \partial_z F = R = \prod_{i=1}^{2^{2^k}} \dot{F}_i = e^{\lambda L} \quad (9)$$

$\rho_{vac}(GR)$ can be clasified by the Friedmann solution with Lagrangian $L = R\dot{R}^2 - \phi_3(R)$ and polynomial

$$V_{T_{global}} \simeq \phi_3(z = \phi_{2^k}) \quad (10)$$

(11) is cubic whenever the Feigenbaum renormalized iterated degree 2^k polynomial ϕ_{2^k} meets cubic roots. Energies of k-components should follow a $1/2^{2^k}$ law. Eq. (4) is quadratic in ρ_{vac} e.g. $\delta m \delta m \simeq 0$

$$\alpha m_+^2 + \beta m_+ m_- + \gamma m_-^2 = 0 \quad (11)$$

Masses m_{\pm} itself are $f(\omega)$ - quadratic due to 4. Hyperelliptic based coefficients are integer $(\alpha\beta\gamma) = (1, -136, 10)$ which recover an electron - to-proton mass ratio up to precision of 10^{-3} [13]. Masses $m_{\pm} \simeq f(\omega)$, $f^2(\omega)$ are related to the areal density ρ_{res} of residua of iterated $f(\omega_k)$. Optimized values ρ_{res} allow to refine (11) and the conjecture about the fine structure constant $\alpha_f^{-1} \simeq 2\pi\delta_F$ [14]. Up to second order $L(\nu[f(\omega)])$ has three-components $1, \partial_z$ and $\partial_z \partial_{z'}$ acting on $\log E$: (i) real matter $\rho_m \simeq \log f(\omega)$ (ii) inert drift-diffusion fields ($\partial_z \log f = 0$) with real ions ρ_{ion} (iii) complex dark matter ρ_{dark} in $L(F, \dot{F}, \ddot{F}, \ddot{\ddot{F}}) \simeq \{F(t, z), z\}$ as sketched in Figure 4.

$$\rho_{vac} \simeq \rho_m + \rho_{ion} + \rho_{dark} \simeq 0 \quad (12)$$

A square in ρ_{vac} in 4 is limited by the identity $\vartheta_{[00]}^4 = \vartheta_{[01]}^4 + \vartheta_{[10]}^4$. The real density $\rho_m = \rho_r + \rho_{exc, vdW}$ is a sum of rest mass ρ_r , excitonic binding energy and quadratic van der Waals interaction $\rho_{exc, vdW}$ which is (3) $\rho_m \simeq T(f) \simeq \partial_f \partial_{f'} \ln \frac{\Delta F}{\Delta f}$. The scale factor and $\frac{\Delta F}{\Delta f} \simeq K(\lambda)$ is a product of theta constants related to quarter periods $K(\lambda)$ [15]. The differential equation for $K(\lambda)$ a local wave function Hermite polynomial with frequency ν_n . Then, $\rho_m = \sum_n \frac{1}{2} \nu_n$ are zero-point oscillations. Rest masses ρ_r are stable iterates of the Big Bang-Big Rip solution for nine discriminants Δ reducing to a φ_3 . The inverse Fermion Green's function G^{-1} in quantum statistics is related to $F(t, z) = \gamma \circ z$ in [2].

Figure 2: Real and complex energies within a BST-environment, variable R is the radius of an apparent singularity (charge, universe) variable z is curvature, ρ_{ion} contains CR [4].

5. Elliptic involution and various vacuum energy minima

Iterated complex unified fields describe a superfluid state of an open universe where self-organization in dissipative structures occurs for closed subsystems, e.g. DPAPP. The claim is that doubly-periodic processed unified fields are capable to exhibit local minima of vacuum energy density. The k -iterated Legendre module $\lambda = \frac{1}{2} + \frac{\bar{\psi}\lambda_m\psi}{m}$ enters FZU as a four-component Dirac current [6] [15] [4]. FZU is an iterated potential flow where vacuum density $\rho_{vac}\{F, z, \lambda\}$ depends on elliptic involution $i(\lambda) = 1 - \lambda$ which solves the longstanding CCP [12] [10]. Iteration steps $\gamma(\phi_3(f(\sqrt{\Delta})) \circ z = F(t, z)$ with change periods ω via discriminants Δ and yield a Gaussian-like diffusion process like measured CR. Quadratic transformed periods $\begin{pmatrix} 1 & -1 \\ 1 & 1 \end{pmatrix}\omega$ obey involution $f(\omega') = \sqrt{2}/f(\omega)$. Equivalent periods $\begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix}\omega, \begin{pmatrix} 0 & -1 \\ 1 & 0 \end{pmatrix}\omega$ obey invariances $\lambda \rightarrow i(\lambda), 1/\lambda, 1/i(\lambda), 1 - 1/\lambda, -\lambda/i(\lambda)$ which are

$$(1 - \lambda i(\lambda))^3 / (\lambda i(\lambda))^2 = const \quad (13)$$

Elliptic involution undercuts a given vacuum energy in a fractal DPAPP as a non-local correlation between low and high values of dimensionless energy density. For energy density $\rho_{core} \simeq 10^1 \text{ gcm}^{-3}$ at ground level and at $\rho_{vac} \simeq 10^{-31} \text{ gcm}^{-3}$ atmospheric level CR air shower moving with velocity of light are correlated with slow plant grow [4]. The density in FZU is like that of a black hole density which is not a well-defined [2] [15]. This uncertainty in density enables a continuous creation of matter in holomorphic environment near zeros of $\xi(z)$ or $\sigma(z)$ which is equivalent to QHT.

6. Plant growth, Air ions and Cooling in Atmosphere

Measured ion fluxes 2 or 20 – 30 $\simeq \text{cm}^{-3}\text{s}^{-1}$ ion-pairs at atmospheric or ground level yield simulated and measured concentrations of about 10^5 cm^{-3} [16, 17] which are negligible ρ_{ion} of about $10^{-11} \text{ kWh} \cdot \text{cm}^{-3}$ in (12). At cloud-radiative forcing atmospheric cooling is attributed to cloud cover changes. At CRCCS atmospheric cooling is attributed to phantom energy ρ_{dark} which compensates created rest mass ρ_m . OMG energy 10^{21} eV at GZK cutoff or the Planck energy $M_p \simeq 10^{-5} \text{ g} \simeq 10^{28} \text{ eV}$ content of a lightning is equivalent to heat or cool 12 g water or an atmospheric cloud of $5 \cdot 10^8 \text{ g}$ by 1°K . Phantom dark matter ρ_{dark} is claimed as a thermodynamic cooling effect. Lightning consist of 5 – 15 Coulomb which are up to 10^{30} charge quanta, i.e. $\#z_{nt}$ in CRCCS. Accordingly, a minimal generated matter of 10^{-5} g is capable to induce a strong energy effect felt as cooling within DPAPP. As a result, one has the relations $\rho_{ion} \ll \rho_{dark}$, ρ_m and $\rho_{dark} \simeq -\rho_m$. Vacuum energies $\rho_{vac}(GR)$, $\rho_{vac}(QS)$ mainly split into positive and negative parts $\rho_m, \rho_{ion}, \rho_{dark}$ which would be capable to explain the Dirac Sea. The DPAPP energy gain $\delta\rho_{dark}$ is achieved by a certain amount of created organic matter which lowers ρ_{dark} . In distinction to the CRCCS gain $\delta\rho_{dark}$ present bioenergy extracts energy from the

excitonic binding energy $\delta\rho_{exc,vdW}$. In distinction to ion-aerosol clear-sky mechanism of condensation nuclei through cloud brightness and cover the CRCCS-cooling effect in $V_{T_{global}}(z)$ is due to complex matter ρ_{dark} . Within CRCCS zeros $\xi(z) = 0$ generate compensating negative phantom energy ρ_{dark} and positive large rest mass energy. Composting within $\xi(z) = 0$ states (4) makes the cooling effect disappear [18] [19] [20].

7. Conclusions

A doubly-periodic processing is a current-current correlation of many participating periods. In natural science it is realized by breathing of plants and living and cellular respiration, photosynthesis. Simultaneous one-periodic cycles of complex energy/time superimposed by one-periodic cycles of complex entropy/temperature are shown to dominate the behavior of zeta functions in the vicinity of nontrivial zeros. Instead of being an exotic state of matter it is a breathing by growing plants and livings being. A fluctuating complex time-thermal contour process is claimed to achieve lower vacuum densities which is capable to derive quantum statistics [21, 22]. Ranges of measured vacuum density vary from general relativistic values $\rho_{vac} \simeq 1 \text{ eV} \cdot \text{cm}^{-3}$, $\rho_{vac}(CMB) \simeq 0,26 \text{ eV} \cdot \text{cm}^{-3}$, $\rho_{vac}(star) \simeq 0,3 \text{ eV} \cdot \text{cm}^{-3}$ which are to at ground level. Theory of the CCP $\rho_{vac}(QS) \simeq 10^{50-20}$, $\rho_{vac}(GR)$ indicates the validity of elliptic involution. CRCCS is based on complex phantom dark energy ρ_{dark} of the order rest energy of a molecule but with opposite sign which would be stored in a DPAPP. DPAPP processing as breathing works on the background of existing branching and ramification in clouds and plant growth and claims a certain amount of ‘creatio ex nihilo’ of matter in zero states $\xi = 0$ or $\sigma = 0$ of a holomorphic atmospheric environment.

References

- [1] Heegner, K. Diophantische Analysis und Modulfunktionen. Mathematische Zeitschrift **56**, 227–253 (1952)
- [2] Ziep, O. Fractal Universe and Atoms. Scholars Journal of Physics, Mathematics and Statistics **12**, 89–96 (2025) [10.36347/sjpms.2025.v12i04.002](https://doi.org/10.36347/sjpms.2025.v12i04.002)
- [3] Dirac, P A M (19M4) Cosmological Models And The Large Numbers Hypothesis, Proceedings of the Royal Society A: Mathematical, Physical and Engineering Sciences, **338**, 439–446. <https://doi.org/10.1098/rspa.1974.0095>
- [4] Ziep, O. Cosmic Rays, Aerosol-Photosynthesis and Vegetational Air Ion. Journal of Modern Physics **16**, 1179–1192 (2025) [10.4236/jmp.2025.168059](https://doi.org/10.4236/jmp.2025.168059)
- [5] Pasko, V.P., Celestin, S., Bourdon, A., Janalizadeh, R., Pervez, Z., Jansky, J., Gourbin, P. Photoelectric Effect in Air explains Lightning Initiation and Terrestrial gamma ray flashes. Journal of Geophysical Research: Atmospheres **13014**, 2025–043897 (2025) [10.1029/2025JD043897](https://doi.org/10.1029/2025JD043897)

- [6] Ziep, O. (2024) Nucleosynthesis in Thin Layers, www.epubli.de, Berlin. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10848593>
 - [7] Ziep, O. A quantum entangled fractal superfluid universe. *Journal of High Energy Physics, Gravitation and Cosmology* **113**, 850–868 (2025) [10.4236/jhepgc.2025.113054](https://doi.org/10.4236/jhepgc.2025.113054).
 - [8] Laughlin, R.B. Anomalous quantum hall effect: an incompressible quantum fluid with fractionally charged excitations. *Physical Review Letters* **5018**, 1395 (1983) [10.1103/PhysRevLett.50.1395](https://doi.org/10.1103/PhysRevLett.50.1395)
 - [9] Haldane, F.D.M. A modular-invariant modified Weierstrass sigma-function as a building block for lowest-landau-level wavefunctions on the torus. *Journal of Mathematical Physics* **59**, 071901 (2018) [10.1063/1.5042618](https://doi.org/10.1063/1.5042618)
 - [10] Ziep, O (2025) Matter and Quantum Entanglement, *Journal of Applied Mathematics and Physics*, **13**, 89–96. <https://doi.org/10.4236/jamp.2025.134059>
 - [11] Hermite, C. Extraits de lettres de m. ch. hermite à m. jacobi sur différents objets de la théorie des nombres. *Journal für die reine und angewandte Mathematik* **40**, 261–278 (1850)
 - [12] Ziep, O. Charge Quanta as Zeros of the Zeta Function in Bifurcated Spacetime. *Journal of Modern Physics* **16**, 249–262 (2025) [10.4236/jmp.2025.162011](https://doi.org/10.4236/jmp.2025.162011)
 - [13] Eddington, A.S. *Relativity Theory of Protons and Electrons*. CUP Archive, (1936)
 - [14] Hieb, M. Feigenbaum Constant and the Sommerfeld Fine-Structure Constant. (1995) <https://www.rxiv.org/abs/1704.0365>
 - [15] Ziep, O. (2024) Fractal Zeta Universe and Cosmic-Ray-Charge-Cloud Superfluid, www.epubli.de, Berlin. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14193126>
 - [16] Yu, F. Altitude variations of cosmic ray induced production of aerosols: Implications for global cloudiness and climate. *Journal of Geophysical Research: Space Physics* **107**, 8 (2002) [10.1029/2001JA000248](https://doi.org/10.1029/2001JA000248)
 - [17] Patil, G B, Pawar, S D , Bhosale,J L and P. G. Patil P G (2021) Pollution Index And Air Ion Variation In Different Vegetation Area At The Rural Station Bhilawadi, *Journal of Physics: Conference Series*, **1964**, 032006. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1088/1742-6596/1964/3/032006>
 - [18] Snow-Kropla, E., Pierce, J., Westervelt, D., Trivitayanurak, W. Cosmic rays, aerosol formation and cloud-condensation nuclei: sensitivities to model uncertainties. *Atmospheric Chemistry and Physics* **118**, 4001–4013 (2011)
 - [19] Svensmark, H.,Svensmark, J.,Enghoff, M.B.,Shaviv, N.J. Atmospheric Ionization and Cloud Radiative Forcing. *Scientific Reports* **11**, 19668 (2021) [10.1038/s41598-021-99033-1](https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-021-99033-1)
-

- [20] Svensmark, H. Influence of Cosmic Rays on Earth's Climate. *Phys. Rev. Lett.* **81**, 5027–5030 (1998) [10.1103/PhysRevLett.81.5027](https://doi.org/10.1103/PhysRevLett.81.5027)
 - [21] Ziep, O (2026) Quantum Statistics and Zeta Functions, to be submitted, <https://doi.org/10.4236/jamp.2025.134059>
 - [22] Ziep, O (2026) **12**, Doubly- Periodic Processing in Particle Accelerators and Fusion Reactors, *Journal of High Energy Physics, Gravitation and Cosmology*, <https://doi.org/10.4236/jamp.2025.134059>
-